

RQ1 Key Queries

Query 1: Generate Seeded Random Subset

```
//Code to create a seeded random 1% subset and label it "MSRSubest"  
// Step 1: Count the total number of Artifact nodes  
MATCH (a:Artifact)  
WITH count(a) AS total_count  
// Step 2: Calculate the number of nodes to select (1% of total)  
WITH total_count, toInteger(total_count * 0.01) AS subset_size  
// Step 3: Match all Artifact nodes and assign a pseudo-seeded random value based on node ID  
MATCH (a:Artifact)  
WITH a, abs(id(a)) % total_count AS seeded_random_value  
// Step 4: Filter to select the calculated number of artifacts  
WHERE seeded_random_value < subset_size  
// Step 5: Add the MSRSubset label to the selected artifacts  
SET a:MSRSubset
```

Query 2: Label subsets of vulnerable artifacts

```
//Create RQ1 Dataset FINAL  
MATCH (a:MSRSubset)-[:relationship_AR]->(r:Release)-[:addedValues]->(av_r:AddedValue  
{type: "CVE"})  
WHERE av_r.value CONTAINS "name"  
//Create Sets  
SET a:RQ1DS1A  
SET r:RQ1DS1R  
SET av_r:RQ1DS1AV
```

Query 3: Pull all vulnerable releases data for exporting to RQ1DS1V2

```
// Query Dataset V2  
// Added dependency count to the returned values using the option match line  
MATCH (a:RQ1DS1A)-[:relationship_AR]->(r:RQ1DS1R)-[:addedValues]->(av_r:RQ1DS1AV)  
OPTIONAL MATCH (r)-[:d:dependency]->(ad:Artifact)  
RETURN  
  id(a) as aID1, a.id as aID2, id(r) as rID1, r.version as releaseVersion, r.timestamp as  
  releaseTimestamp, COUNT(d) AS dependencyCount, id(av_r) as avID1, av_r.value as  
  CVEValues
```

Query 4: Pull all non-vulnerable releases data for exporting to RQ1DS1V2EXTRA

```
// Query Dataset V2 Extra Data
```

```

// Returns extra values in extra columns instead of having it all be in one column
MATCH (a:RQ1DS1A)-[:relationship_AR]->(r:Release)
WHERE NOT r:RQ1DS1R
OPTIONAL MATCH (r)-[d:dependency]->(ad:Artifact)
OPTIONAL MATCH (r)-[:addedValues]->(av_r:RQ1DS1AV)
RETURN
  id(a) as aID1,
  a.id as aID2,
  id(r) as rID1,
  r.version as releaseVersion,
  r.timestamp as releaseTimestamp,
  COUNT(d) AS dependencyCount,
  id(av_r) as avID1,
  av_r.value as CVEValues

```

RQ2 Key Queries:

Establishing Seeded Random Subset

```

//Code to create a seeded random 1% subset and label it "MSRSubest"
// Step 1: Count the total number of Artifact nodes
MATCH (a:Artifact)
WITH count(a) AS total_count

// Step 2: Calculate the number of nodes to select (1% of total)
WITH total_count, toInteger(total_count * 0.01) AS subset_size

// Step 3: Match all Artifact nodes and assign a pseudo-seeded random value based on node ID
MATCH (a:Artifact)
WITH a, abs(id(a)) % total_count AS seeded_random_value

// Step 4: Filter to select the calculated number of artifacts
WHERE seeded_random_value < subset_size

// Step 5: Add the MSRSubset label to the selected artifacts
SET a:MSRSubset

```

Locating & Labeling Vulnerable Artifact Release Nodes with Active CVE's

```

//Code to label releases containing non-empty CVE's within the MSRSubset

```

```
// Step 1: Match releases in MSRSUBSET that have CVEs containing "name"
MATCH (r:MSRSUBSET)-[:relationship_AR]->(release:Release)-[:addedValues]->(av:AddedValue
{type: "CVE"})
WHERE av.value CONTAINS "name"
```

```
// Step 2: Set the label "ActiveCVE" on the matched releases
SET release:ActiveCVE
```

```
// Optional: Return the labeled releases for confirmation
RETURN release
```

Establishing the Release Nodes with vulnerable dependencies to the infected Artifacts

```
MATCH (pot_vul_release:PVR)-[d:dependency]->(vulnerable_artifact:ActiveCVEa)
MATCH (vulnerable_artifact)-[:relationship_AR]->(vuln_release:ActiveCVEr)
WHERE vuln_release.version = d.targetVersion
RETURN pot_vul_release, d, vulnerable_artifact, vuln_release
```

Retrieve Freshness Scores from Release's av Freshness Node

```
//Code to get Freshness score from the Freshness node attached to vulnerable releases. Need
APOC plugin
// Step 1: Match artifacts with freshness scores
MATCH
(a:MSRSUBSET)-[:relationship_AR]->(r:Release:RQ2Vul_Releases)-[:addedValues]->(av_fresh:A
ddedValue)
WHERE av_fresh.type = "FRESHNESS" AND av_fresh.value IS NOT NULL

// Step 2: Clean the JSON string by removing backslashes using double escaping
WITH a, r, apoc.text.replace(av_fresh.value, '\\\\', '\\') AS cleaned_value

// Step 3: Parse the cleaned JSON string
WITH a, r, apoc.convert.fromJsonMap(cleaned_value) AS freshness_data

// Step 4: Extract numberMissedRelease
WITH a, r, freshness_data["freshness"]["numberMissedRelease"] AS FreshnessScore

// Step 5: Return the result
RETURN a, r, FreshnessScore
ORDER BY FreshnessScore ASC
```

Find the CVE's in subset and all Release Nodes containing these CVE's

```
// Step 1: Match releases and their associated CVE nodes
MATCH (release:Release:ActiveCVE)-[:addedValues]->(cveNode:AddedValue)
WHERE cveNode.value CONTAINS "cve"

// Step 2: Clean and parse the JSON string
WITH release, cveNode,
    apoc.text.replace(cveNode.value, "\\\"", "") AS cleanJson
WITH release, apoc.convert.fromJsonMap(cleanJson) AS parsedValue

// Step 3: Extract CVE names
UNWIND parsedValue.cve AS cveEntry
WITH release, cveEntry.name AS cveName

// Step 4: Group by CVE names and collect associated releases
WITH cveName, collect(release.id) AS associatedReleases

// Step 5: Order by CVE name and return results
RETURN cveName AS CVE, associatedReleases AS Releases
ORDER BY CVE
```

Finding the timestamp of the first release after vulnerable dependency has been dropped

```
// Step 1: Match releases and their associated CVE nodes
MATCH (release:Release:ActiveCVE)-[:addedValues]->(cveNode:AddedValue)
WHERE cveNode.value CONTAINS "cve"
WITH cveNode, release

// Step 2: Clean and parse the JSON string
WITH release, cveNode,
    apoc.text.replace(cveNode.value, "\\\"", "") AS cleanJson
WITH release, apoc.convert.fromJsonMap(cleanJson) AS parsedValue, cveNode

// Step 3: Extract CVE names
UNWIND parsedValue.cve AS cveEntry
WITH release, cveEntry.name AS cveName, cveNode

// Step 4: Get the artifact ID from the releases
MATCH (release)<-[:relationship_AR]-(userArtifact:Artifact)
WITH release, cveName, userArtifact, cveNode
```

```
// Step 5: Find the earliest timestamp for the artifact
WITH userArtifact, cveName, MIN(release.timestamp) AS earliestTimestamp
```

```
// Step 6: Find the latest timestamp for the artifact
MATCH (latestRelease:Release)-[:relationship_AR]->(userArtifact)
WHERE latestRelease.timestamp > earliestTimestamp
WITH userArtifact, cveName, earliestTimestamp, MAX(latestRelease.timestamp) AS
latestTimestamp
```

```
// Step 7: Find the next release after the latest release (called "cleanRelease")
MATCH (cleanRelease:Release)-[:relationship_AR]->(userArtifact)
WHERE cleanRelease.timestamp > latestTimestamp
WITH userArtifact, cveName, earliestTimestamp, latestTimestamp, cleanRelease.timestamp AS
timeDropped
```

```
// Step 8: Return the results
RETURN userArtifact.id AS artifactID, cveName AS associatedCVE, earliestTimestamp AS
earliestReleaseTimestamp, latestTimestamp AS latestReleaseTimestamp, timeDropped
ORDER BY timeDropped
```

Create a next release relationship of releases from the same artifact based on release timestamps

```
MATCH (ua:UserArtifact)
WITH ua
ORDER BY ua.id // Ensure a consistent ordering
SKIP 0 LIMIT 1000
CALL {
  WITH ua
  MATCH (ua)-[:relationship_AR]->(u:Release)
  WITH ua, u
  ORDER BY u.timestamp ASC
  WITH ua, COLLECT(u) AS releases
  UNWIND releases AS currentRelease
  WITH ua, currentRelease, releases, apoc.coll.indexOf(releases, currentRelease) AS idx
  WITH ua, currentRelease, releases[idx + 1] AS nextRelease
  WHERE nextRelease IS NOT NULL
  MERGE (currentRelease)-[:nextRelease]->(nextRelease)
```

Create a label “firstCleanRelease” for the release after the last vulnerable user release connected to a User Artifact. This first clean release timestamp will represent the time the vulnerable dependency was dropped.

```
MATCH (lastVulRelease:Release>LastVulRelease)-[:nextRelease]->(firstCleanRelease:Release)
SET firstCleanRelease:FirstCleanRelease
RETURN firstCleanRelease
```

Create a property key “FreshnessScore” for the the last vulnerable user release connected to a User Artifact. Any with a score of “0” are still actively vulnerable.

```
// Step 1: Match artifacts with freshness scores
MATCH
(a:UserArtifact)-[relationship_AR]->(r:LastVulRelease)-[:addedValues]->(av_fresh:AddedValue)
WHERE av_fresh.type = "FRESHNESS" AND av_fresh.value IS NOT NULL

// Step 2: Clean the JSON string by removing backslashes using double escaping
WITH a, r, av_fresh, apoc.text.replace(av_fresh.value, '\\', '\\\\') AS cleaned_value

// Step 3: Parse the cleaned JSON string
WITH a, r, apoc.convert.fromJsonMap(cleaned_value) AS freshness_data

// Step 4: Extract numberMissedRelease and set it as a property on the LastVulRelease node
SET r.FreshnessScore = freshness_data['freshness']['numberMissedRelease']

// Step 5: Return the updated nodes for verification
RETURN r, r.FreshnessScore
ORDER BY r.FreshnessScore DESC
```

RQ3 Key Queries

Code to create a seeded random 1% subset and label it "MSRSubset"

```
// Step 1: Count the total number of Artifact nodes
MATCH (a:Artifact)
WITH count(a) AS total_count
```

```
// Step 2: Calculate the number of nodes to select (1% of total)
WITH total_count, toInteger(total_count * 0.01) AS subset_size
```

```
// Step 3: Match all Artifact nodes and assign a pseudo-seeded random value based on node ID
MATCH (a:Artifact)
WITH a, abs(id(a)) % total_count AS seeded_random_value
```

```
// Step 4: Filter to select the calculated number of artifacts
WHERE seeded_random_value < subset_size
```

```
// Step 5: Add the MSRSubset label to the selected artifacts
SET a:MSRSubset
```

Query to retrieve popularity scores from MSRSubset

```
MATCH (a:MSRSubset)-[:relationship_AR]->(r:Release)-[:addedValues]->(av_pop:AddedValue)
WHERE av_pop.type = "POPULARITY_1_YEAR" AND av_pop.value IS NOT NULL
```

```
//Return all popularity scores
RETURN
  a AS artifact,
  r AS release,
  toFloat(av_pop.value) AS popularity_score
ORDER BY popularity_score DESC;
```

Query to retrieve information from MSRSubset

```
MATCH (a:MSRSubset)-[:relationship_AR]->(r:Release)-[:addedValues]->(av:AddedValue {type:
"CVE"})
  WHERE av.value CONTAINS "name"
```

```
// Return all popularity scores
RETURN
  a AS artifact,
  r AS release,
  av.value AS cve
```

Query to get transitive vulnerability information within the scope of the MSRsubset artifacts (not considering outside artifacts)

```
MATCH (a:MSRSubset)-[:relationship_AR]->(r:Release)
MATCH (r)-[d:dependency]->(depArtifact:Artifact)
  WHERE depArtifact:MSRSubset
```

```

MATCH (depArtifact)-[:relationship_AR]->(depRelease:Release)
  WHERE depRelease.version = d.targetVersion
MATCH (depRelease)-[:addedValues]->(av:AddedValue {type: "CVE"})
  WHERE av.value CONTAINS "name"
WITH a, r, d, depArtifact, depRelease, av
OPTIONAL MATCH (r)-[:addedValues]->(avr_c:AddedValue {type: "CVE"})
  WHERE av.value IS NOT NULL
OPTIONAL MATCH (r)-[:addedValues]->(avr_f:AddedValue {type: "FRESHNESS"})
WHERE avr_f.value IS NOT NULL
OPTIONAL MATCH (r)-[:addedValues]->(avr_p:AddedValue {type: "POPULARITY_1_YEAR"})
WHERE avr_p.value IS NOT NULL
OPTIONAL MATCH (depRelease)-[:addedValues]->(avrd_f:AddedValue {type: "FRESHNESS"})
WHERE avrd_f.value IS NOT NULL
OPTIONAL MATCH (depRelease)-[:addedValues]->(avrd_p:AddedValue {type:
"POPULARITY_1_YEAR"})
WHERE avrd_p IS NOT NULL
WITH a, r, d, depArtifact, av, avrd_f, avrd_p, depRelease, avr_p, avr_f, avr_c
RETURN
  id(a) AS artifactID,
  a.id AS artifactName,
  id(r) AS directReleaseID,
  r.version AS directReleaseVersion,
  r.timestamp AS directReleaseTimeStamp,
  avr_c.value AS directReleaseCVE,
  avr_p.value AS directReleasePopularity,
  avr_f.value AS directReleaseFreshness,
  id(depArtifact) AS dependencyArtifactID,
  depArtifact.id AS dependencyArtifactName,
  id(depRelease) AS depVulReleaseID,
  depRelease.version AS depVulReleaseVersion,
  depRelease.timestamp AS depVulReleaseTimeStamp,
  avrd_f.value AS depVulReleaseFreshness,
  avrd_p.value AS depVulReleasePopularity,
  av.value AS depVulReleaseCVEValue
ORDER BY artifactID

```

Query to get the total number of transitive dependencies for artifacts within scope

```

MATCH (a:MSRSubset)-[:relationship_AR]->(r:Release)
OPTIONAL MATCH (r)-[d:dependency]->(depArtifact:Artifact)
  WHERE depArtifact:MSRSubset
OPTIONAL MATCH (r)-[d:dependency]->(depArtifact2:Artifact)

```

```

WHERE depArtifact2:OutofScope
RETURN
id(a) AS ArtifactID,
a.id AS ArtifactName,
COUNT(DISTINCT d) AS totalNumOfDependencies,
COUNT(DISTINCT id(depArtifact)) AS totalNumOfArtifacts,
COUNT(DISTINCT l) AS totalNumOfDependencies2,
COUNT(DISTINCT id(depArtifact2)) AS totalNumOfArtifacts2

```

Query to get entire MSRSUBSET information (direct vulnerabilities and other info, speed excluded)

```

MATCH (a:AndreasDS1A)-[:relationship_AR]->(r:Release)
OPTIONAL MATCH (r)-[:addedValues]->(av:AddedValue {type: "CVE"})
WHERE av.value CONTAINS "name"
OPTIONAL MATCH (r)-[:addedValues]->(av_f:AddedValue {type: "FRESHNESS"})
WHERE av_f.value IS NOT NULL
OPTIONAL MATCH (r)-[:addedValues]->(av_p:AddedValue {type: "POPULARITY_1_YEAR"})
WHERE av_p.value IS NOT NULL
RETURN
id(a) AS artifactID,
a.id AS artifactName,
id(r) AS ReleaseID,
r.version AS ReleaseVersion,
r.timestamp AS ReleaseTimeStamp,
av.value AS ReleaseCVE,
av_p.value AS ReleasePopularity,
av_f.value AS ReleaseFreshness

```